

COMMUNICATIVE ASPECT OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SPECIALTY

Mirzoyev Jamshed

*Teacher of
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

Abstract: This article analyzes the communicative-cumulative aspects of teaching English as a specialty. Problems and shortcomings in the process of teaching English as a specialist were studied, and the newest innovative methods were discussed.

Key words: Communicative aspects, teaching methods, education system, methodological trainings, culture.

The professional and pedagogical training of a teacher at a university is a multi-component system that combines relatively independent, but interrelated and interdependent components, such as: socio-political, special scientific, psychological-pedagogical and general cultural. One of the most important components of the teacher's education system at the university is his methodological training. The history of foreign language teaching methods knows many attempts to find the most rational way of teaching a foreign language.

Over time, the goals of teaching a foreign language and the requirements for mastering it have changed. An effective impetus for the emergence of a new technology in teaching foreign languages at the present stage was a change in the state of society, the processes of globalization. There was a need to create an alternative method of teaching languages. Training should be more functional, more pragmatic. The communicative function of language came to the fore, which contributed to the creation of a new method in the language teaching system. There are two different approaches to the nature of language: one of them claims that thinking and cognition of the world do not depend on language, which is only a tool

for communication between people; The second approach says that the world is known through language, the essence of which is not only in the transfer of thought from one person to another, but it performs the function of a carrier and custodian of a person's thoughts and knowledge. Today it can be argued that the second principle - the principle of the unity of language and national culture - reflects the latest research in the field of the nature of language.

Until the 80s. of the last century in teaching foreign languages, in foreign language textbooks, nominative speech was limited to naming an object, as in the following sentences: This is a book. He is a pupil. The examples show that when studying pronouns, students are engaged in naming objects, but not in verbal communication. This method, as well as translation, direct and comparative in their practice, taught nominative speech, which has now become insufficient, and the methods have become obsolete [4]. Speaking about the functions of the language, linguists single out the social functions of the language. "The implementation of the possibilities of its organization and development inherent in the language itself, one way or another, is predetermined by social factors related to the functions of the language in society" [5]. Through speech activity, the impact on the language is carried out, subsequently they are reflected in the language itself. Leontiev identifies several functions of speech, in the field of communication he notes the communicative function, considering it a function of regulating behavior.

Language, of course, is a means of communication, but not only. The communicative function of the language is the main one, and the language, as mentioned above, is the "keeper and spokesman" of culture, and along with the communicative function, it has a cumulative function. A cumulative function - or cumulative, where the language not only conveys a message, but also reflects, fixes and stores information about the activity comprehended by a person in linguistic units. The society has its own historical development, and the inherited language is the repository of accumulated experience and the connecting link. Language fully reflects culture at any moment of its development. The cumulative (accumulative)

function of language corresponds to the static plan of cognition, that is, to consciousness, which makes thinking possible. At all levels, the language collects and retains such information, but the cumulative function is primarily provided by the structural language units - vocabulary, phraseology and linguistic aphorism [2]. Being a social phenomenon, language acts as a custodian of information about the world of people of a certain cultural and linguistic community of people, being a "mirror of national culture" [2]. We agree with the opinion of E.M. Vereshchagin and V.G. Kostomarov, who in their studies note that the word contains and stores knowledge about reality. Ideas, information, thoughts are "hung" on the lexeme (the external form of the word), the whole external world passes through words. From a philosophical point of view, the plan of the content of the language can be equated to the level of cognition of the surrounding reality that exists in the cultural and linguistic community, i.e. to public consciousness. The plan of expression of the word - a lexeme, is the material basis for fixing the body of knowledge, which the linguistic community refers to the class of objects and phenomena.

The philosophical principle of the unity of language and consciousness extends not only to the lexical concept, but also to the concept, which "is a unit of collective consciousness, reflecting the subject of the real or ideal world and stored in the national memory of native speakers in a verbally designated form" [1]. The concept is a form of existence of social consciousness in the language, which is a part of the language, and the cumulative function is reflected in the concepts recognized by the content plan of the linguistic sign, from which it follows that, in addition to the subject relatedness, it includes all communicatively significant information [3]. We believe that the concept is a fixer of information that is transmitted in acts of communication, therefore, knowledge and information are transmitted in acts of communication, but are accumulated and fixed in concepts. These conclusions are important for use in teaching students who study a foreign language, getting acquainted with the culture of the language being studied. Cumulative speech, along with communicative speech, can be included in the

teaching of foreign languages, because, as mentioned above, the language is the guardian of the culture of the people, which finds its expression through intercultural communication. Intercultural communication is an adequate mutual understanding of two participants in a communicative act belonging to different linguistic cultures. The subject of intercultural communication is a concept, an ideal essence, independent of lexical units. At the same time, language acts as a means of materializing the concept for communicative purposes.

Well-known methodologist professor D. D. Dzhalalov proposes to introduce a new scientific term communicative-cumulative method [4]. This method has absorbed the modern principles of teaching a foreign language, and the object of cumulative speech is culture as a social repository. Generalization of points of view on the concept and its definitions in linguoculturology allows us to come to the following conclusion: the concept is a unit of collective knowledge/consciousness (sending to the highest spiritual values), which has a linguistic expression and is marked by ethnocultural specifics. Common in this definition and in the definitions of the concept, as well as in the definitions of representation and meaning, remains a generic feature - belonging to the realm of the ideal, while specific differences (the form of knowledge / consciousness - logical / rational, psychological / figurative, linguistic) are neutralized, and their place is taken by verbalization and ethnocultural marking. A large number of scientific papers on the study of concepts makes it possible to use them in the process of teaching a foreign language in all the multilayered cultural phenomena, features of the mentality, the picture of the world of the native speaker of this language. Teaching English with the help of concepts is one of the new ways of modern methodology, using the latest discoveries in the field of linguoculturology and intercultural communication. From the point of view of didactics, we can talk about a triad: the cultural consciousness of students, the consciousness of native speakers of the language being studied, and the consciousness of the teacher. At the same time, the student has the opportunity to realize that his "national-linguistic picture of the world" is not the only possible and

not the only adequate one, that there is another one - for those for whom the studied language is native, - no less correctly reflecting universal needs and interests. It should be presented as cognitive values, which are designed to significantly enrich the horizons of the native speakers of the language being studied. The language is studied for the purpose of communication, dialogue with people of another culture, for a better understanding of oneself, one's culture.

The linguoculturological aspect of language teaching solves the problem of educational material. To the traditional aspects of teaching - phonetic, lexical, grammatical and stylistic, one more is added - linguoculturological. This aspect has always been present in the practice of work, but was not realized and was not distinguished as an independent methodological unit. The linguistic and cultural aspect of the formation of students' communicative and cumulative competence in English at a university should include the national cultural components of the language units of the country of the language being studied. Realia words cover the national cultural layer of vocabulary, i.e. these are words, phrases that name real objects of life, the life of the people; these are words and expressions containing a national-cultural component and denoting objects, samples of folklore, holidays. All this requires consistent work on the selection of vocabulary and the creation of a well-thought-out system for the phased introduction of such vocabulary and expressions into the educational process. Equally important is the immersion of students in the realities of the country of the language being studied. This can be done most effectively by studying holidays, for example, in English-speaking countries, by students studying English as a specialty. Conducting special classes dedicated to a particular holiday, where the student will be familiarized with the text, in which all aspects, features of a particular holiday are noted, according to the holiday celebrated by a decorated audience, etc.

An important fact can be the use in the learning process of both authentic and adapted literary texts, saturated with vocabulary with a national-cultural component of semantics. It is also necessary to develop an effective system of speech exercises

for the assimilation and consolidation of vocabulary with a national-cultural component of semantics, as well as to use linguocultural material containing the realities of English culture: paintings, music, drama, cinema, painting, sculpture, etc.

REFERENCES:

1. Babushkin L.P. Concepts of different types in vocabulary and phraseology and methods for their identification // Methodological problems of cognitive linguistics. - Voronej, 2011.
2. Vereshchagin E.M., Kostomarov V.G. Language and Culture: Linguistics and Regional Studies in Teaching English as a Foreign Language. - 4th ed. - 2019.
3. Vorkachev S. G. Cultural concept and meaning // Proceedings of the Kuban State Technological University. Ser. Humanitarian sciences. - T. 17, no. 2. - Krasnodar, 2013.
4. Jalolov J.J. Chet til vositasida madniyatlararo mulokotni urgatish yoki communicative-cumulative technique of hususida // Proceedings of the scientific and practical conference: Intercultural communication: theory and practice. - T., 2019.
5. Leontiev A.A. Language. Speech. Speech activity. - M : Education, 2009.
6. Mirzoyev, J. (2022). HOFIZ SHEROZIY G'AZALIDAGI NOZIK JIHATLARINING TARJIMADA BERILISHI.(FORS-INGLIZ TILLARI MISOLIDA). *Ученый XXI века*, (5-1 (86)), 83-85.
7. Daminov, N. K. (2022). The Role of Simultaneous Interpretation in the System of Types of Translation. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 5(11), 10-15.
8. ДАМИНОВ, Н. К. (2021). WAYS OF COMPRESSION USED IN THE PROCESS OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(6).
9. Kudratovich, D. N. (2021). Psycho linguistic features of simultaneous interpretation. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 360-365.

10. Ибаев, А. (2021). Comparative syntactic devices as an object of language study. *Общество и инновации*, 2(8/S), 153-159.
11. Дарвишов, И. (2020). Этнослараро тил муносабатлари (Жануби-ғарбий Наманган шевалари асосида). *Oriental Art and Culture*, (I (2)), 166-175.